

Review of Phytochemical and Antimicrobial Property of valuable medicinal plant *Aloe vera*

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Abstract: It has been demonstrated that *Aloe vera* offers a range of pharmacological advantages, including those for the treatment of inflammation, immunological regulation, antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, antiproliferative, antidiabetic, laxative, wound healing, moisturizing, anti-aging, and skin protection property.

1. INTRODUCTION: -

The beneficial medical plant *Aloe vera* contains a number of active compounds. Aloe is a genus with approximately 430 species that is found all over the world and thrives in hot climates (Debnath et al., 2018). This plant resembles a cactus in shape. One of the common plants found in India, Aloe vera has been shown to have a number of pharmacological benefits, including those for treating inflammation, immune modulation, antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, antiproliferative, antidiabetic, laxative, wound healing, moisturising, anti-aging, and skin protection. A technique for figuring out which components are present in the plant is phytochemical screening.

2. PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS: -

2.1 Fresh leaves:

Aloe vera fresh leaves were used in a 2017 study by Dharajiya et al. using the cold maceration method. Alkaloids, saponins, sterols, flavonoids, and phenols are all present in methanol, along with phenols, alkaloids, saponins, and sterols in hexane, ethyl acetate, and aqueous solvents. Alkaloids, tannins, sterols, flavonoids, and phenols are all present in aqueous solvents.

El Sayed et al. (2016) reported phenolic acids, caffeoylquinic acid hexoside, 3, 4-O-(E) caffeoyl feruloyl quinin acid, aloeresin E, isoaloesin D, and 2'-O-feruloylaloerin flavonoids, Orientin, vicenin II, and lucenin II in methanolic extract. The chromones aloesin, 8-C-glucosyl-7-O-methyl-(S)-aloesol, and isoaloesin D were identified by Park MK et al. in 1998 studies. Aloe emodin, aloenin and aloenin B Anthrones, 8-O-methyl-7-hydroxyaloin A and B, and 10-hydroxyaloin A in ethanolic extract. Phenyl pyrones. In an acetone extract, sinapic acid, chlorogenic acid, aloin, aloemodin 8-O-beta-D-glucopyranoside, catechin, and epicatechin were identified by Lai Q et al. in 2016. Malik et al. 2017 determined Cardiac glycosides, sterols, flavonoids, reducing sugar, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, carbohydrates, amino acids, tannins, and saponin glycosides which were extracted with methanol, ethanol and hot water. Añibarro-Ortega M et al. 2019 reported dietary fiber (mannan), malic acid, α -tocopherol, phenolic compounds, and apigenin glycoside derivatives were extracted to petroleum ether and ethanol water. Palermo et al. 2013 reported Phytosterols (β -sitosterol) in green leaves of *Aloe vera*. Aldehydes; 4-ethylbenzaldehyde and benzene acetaldehyde Acids; lauric acid, palmitic acid Carboxylic acids; hydroxy octanoic acid derivative, octadecanoic acid Alkanes; hexadecane derivative were extracted with hexane, reported Dey P et al. 2017. Mariappan V et al. 2012 studied

terpenoids, tannins, flavonoids, resins, anthraquinones, saponins, glycosides, acidic compounds, lignin, semi anthraquinone like derivatives, polysaccharides, vitamin B complex, phenol chromones, and chromones were extracted with 95% ethanol from leaves part of *Aloe vera*. Ranghoo-Sanmukhiya et al. 2010 reported that alkaloids, anthraquinones, terpenes, phenols, tannins, coumarins, and flavonoids present in leaves part of *Aloe vera* and extracted with dichloromethane and methanol solvent system.

2.2 Dried Leaves of Aloe Vera:

Kumar et al. 2017 extracted alkaloids, phenols, flavonoids, saponins, glycosides, reducing sugars, phenolic compounds, tannins, steroids, and terpenoids from dried leaves with methanol. Arun Kumar et al. 2009 studied flavonoids, tannins, and saponins terpenoids; Squalene, phytol, and lupeol Alkynes; 1-Tetradecyne and 1-Octadecyne Carboxylic acids; Tridecanoic acid and n-Hexadecanoic acid Alkanes; 1-Iodo-2-methylundecane, eicosane, octadecane, 2-methyl nonadecane, and tetracontane, 3,5,24-trimethyl-C Fatty acids; Oleic acid Dicarboxylic acid; Oxalic acid Alcohol; 1-Octanol Ester; 2-butyl- didodecyl phthalate Vitamins; α -Tocopherol and vitamin E Sterols; β -Sitosterol were extracted Soxhlet extraction method with help of distilled water, ethanol, acetone solution. Anthraquinones, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, squalene, oleic acid, dodecanoic acid, p-xylene, and n-hexadecanoic acid Sathyaprabha G et al. 2010. Saponins, phytosterols, terpenoids, alkaloids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, proteins, phenols, and carbohydrates found in 80% ethanolic extract of dried leaves which was reported by Karpagam et al. 2019. Raphael E. 2012 reported tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids, carbohydrates, and alkaloids in dried leaves of *Aloe vera* where chloroform and water were used as extraction solvents.

2.3 Leaf Gel of Aloe Vera:

Fatty acids; hexadecenoic acid, octadecanoic acid, and 9-octadenoic acid Sterols; Sitosterol, and stigmasterol Alcohols; 1-octadecanol, 1-dodecanol Alkanes; debocane, tricosane, and 4-methyl, 1- (phenylthioxomethyl) piperidine were extracted from ethanolic crude extract. Okamura N et al. 1998 observed Chromones; 8-C-glucosyl-(2'-O-cinnamoyl)-7-O-methylaloediol A and B, 8-C-glucosyl-noreugenin, 4'-O-glucosyl-isoaloeresin DII, and 4'-Oglucosyl-isoaloeresin DI. Tanaka M et al. 2006 worked on leaf gel of *Aloe vera* and found phytosterols; cycloartenol, lophenol, 24-ethyl-lophenol, 24-methyllophenol, and 24-methylene-cycloartanol. Maloyl glucans, Veracylglucan A, B, and C were observed by Esua MF et al. 2006. Lawrence R et al. 2009 studied pyrocatechol, ascorbic acid, coumaric acid, and p-coumaric acid. Nejat-zadeh-Barandozi F 2013 reported alkaloids, aldehydes, phytosterols, pyrimidines, phenolic acids/ polyphenols, fatty acids, alkanes, organic acids, alcohols, dicarboxylic acids, ketones, and indoles. Mariappan V et al. 2012 observed carbohydrates, resins, reducing sugars, glucuronic acid, pentose derivatives, acetylated mannan, galactoglucoarabinomannan, glucomannan, and monosaccharides (alverose). Cardiotionic glycosides, anthraglycosides, mucilage's, and reducing sugars reported by Vazquez B et al. 1996. Kammoun M et al. 2011 observed sterols type 5 and anthraquinones, triterpenoids, carbohydrates, saponins, anthraquinones, and naphthoquinones while leaf skin contains steroids, tannins, terpenoids, catechin, carotenoids, and anthraquinones. Phenolic compounds; Sinapic acid, catechin, and quercetin were reported in leaf gel by Debnath T et al. 2018.

3. ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY: -

Prakash P Athiban et al. 2012 reported that *Aloe vera* extract were used against three bacterial strains i.e., *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and found 24 mm, 21 mm and 24 mm inhibition zones respectively. Jain S. et al. 2016 studied *Aloe vera* gel affectivity against oral pathogens which were *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, *Clostridium bacilli*, *S. mutans* and *Staph. Aureus* and the concentration average zone of inhibition measured was 6.9mm in *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, 6.3mm in *Clostridium bacilli*, 6.8mm in *S. mutans* and 6.6mm in *Staph aureus*.

Ciprofloxacin (30mcg) showed 7.4mm zone of inhibition against *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, 7.1 mm against *Clostridium bacilli*, 6.8mm and 7.3mm against *S. mutans* and *Staph. aureus* respectively. The Ofloxacin (5mcg) showed zone of inhibition against *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, *Clostridium bacilli*, *S. mutans* and *Staph. aureus* respectively.

4. CONCLUSION: -

One of the most useful and significant medicinal herbs is *A. vera*. These days, both conventional and modern medicine employ these herbs. They generate a number of significant phytoconstituents that are in great demand both domestically and abroad.

5. REFERENCES: -

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